

1 **An early immune and senescence phenotype associated with BRCA1/2 mutation or loss.**

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6 We combined study of total transcription across multiple settings to try and distinguish or temporally
7 separate BRCA1/2-resulting defects. We recently described inappropriate activation of homeobox
8 transcription factors as a primary, cell-intrinsic molecular defect in humans with breast cancer containing a
9 BRCA mutation. We describe here an early immune and senescence phenotype associated with BRCA1/2
10 mutation or loss that appeared to involve interactions with immune cells or other cell types. In the breast of
11 humans with germline BRCA2 mutation, an altered NK signature was present prior to transformation
12 featuring changes in expression of killer cell associated markers CD160, CD84, CD80, CD244, CD247,
13 CD248 and NKG7. In HEK293, deletion of BRCA2 resulted in CD68, CD163L1, CD70 and CD109, but
14 silencing of CD9 and CD320. This was accompanied by activation of IRF1 and IRF3. Brca mutation is
15 characterized by an immune and senescence phenotype that features aspects of the killer cell gene
16 signature.

17 Citations

18 Sedic, M., Skibinski, A., Brown, N., Gallardo, M., Mulligan, P., Martinez, P., Keller, P.J., Glover, E.,
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20 cell-type-specific genomic instability and premature senescence. Nature communications, 6(1), p.7505.
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